

**Symbolism of the Masonic tools and elements of the Alpha & Omega triptych.
The Sephirot present in the Tracing Board.
Collection of words from Freemasons, concerning tools and elements.**

SEBÖK Ferenc, 2024.

Triptyque Alpha & Omega, 28X54, acrylique et encres, sur carton, 28x54, Sebök Ferenc. Collection de la RL° France 9, Orient de Budapest, (H).

1. Preliminary

The work that I suggest here is the presentation of a painted triptych concerning the three degrees of the Blue Lodge. I was inspired by different rites : modern Belgian ritual, ancient and accepted Scottish ritual and French ritual.

An important principle guided me in this work, namely that everything is perception and that perceptions are subjective. In addition to the study of rituals and theoretical research on the authors, this work aimed to capture the perceptions and mental representations concerning symbolic tools and elements among Freemasons, as well as my own perceptions and understanding of these elements and tools.

The people interviewed wanted to remain anonymous. The sample concerns 60 masons met who gave their perceptions and understanding of the symbolic tools, elements and symbolism in Freemasonry. This is therefore a research work where the important thing was the qualitative rather than quantitative approach. This work represents the synthesis of the research.

The only part where the theoretical approach was the most striking is the Sephirot approach. However, I wanted to add the Masonic dimension.

2. Warning about the construction of the Triptych

The construction of the triptych is based on the reading of rituals, the approach to the Sephirot, my perception of things and the perception of the Brother Masons in my sample (=60). After recording the perceptions on the symbolism of the tools and elements appearing on the triptych, I captured the salient perceptions and understandings to note them in this work.

I must specify that the chosen triptych represents the first degree, that of the Apprentice, the second degree of Companion in the middle, and finally on the right, the degree of Master. This initial precision is important, because the three degrees (Apprentice, Follow craft and Master) contain tools or representations that can be found in different degrees. On the other hand, I chose to place certain elements or tools in one place and not another.

For example, the seven stars are found at the second (Follow craft) degree, but they could also be found at the Apprentice or Master degree. The same goes for the lake of love represented in the Apprentice degree, but which could appear in the other two degrees. The Sephirot could also appear in each degree. At the second degree, there are three gavels representing the three officers leading the Lodge: the Worshipful Master, the first warden (Senior warden in the Scottish rite) and the second warden (Junior warden in the Scottish rite). I could have included the 3 mallets also in the other degrees. At the first degree is the Yod surrounded by concentric circles, representing the time which symbolically stops when the masons work in the lodge, and so on...

As the triptych is a representation of the three degrees of the Blue Lodge, I wanted to avoid redundancies as much as possible.

To emphasize the fact that the triptych represents "a whole", the three degrees are framed by a column that of the North, on the Tracing Board concerning the Apprentice degree and by a column, that of the South, on the Tracing Board concerning the Master degree.

On the North Column, we can see three triangles, referring, especially to the three degrees, but also to the number three and the 3 lights directing the lodge. On the South Column, we can see rectangles (long squares, 3 black and 3 white, so 6 in total) reminiscent of the Mosaic Pavement.

This reminder is important to say that the Brothers work on the two Columns, but are only men with imperfections and inclinations that we must overcome. In some rites, the Brother Second Warden (Senior warden) is in the West (Northern Column) and the Brother First Warden (Senior warden) is in the South (Southern Column), in others, it will be the reverse.

It should be noted that in Freemasonry and in certain obediences, the three Great Lights of Freemasonry are the square, the compass and the ruler. In other Obediences, the three Great Lights is the Volume of the Sacred Law (Bible), the square and the compass. In some Lodges, we can see the Bible, the Torah and the Coran displayed on the Altar.

Here is an extract from the modern Belgian ritual, but similar on some levels to the French ritual and with strong similarities in many respects to the ancient and accepted Scottish ritual :

W°M°: J°W°, where is your place in the Lodge?

JW°: In the South, W°M°.

W°M°: Why are you placed like this?

J°W°: To better observe the Sun at its meridian, ...

W°M°: J°W°, where is your place in the Lodge?

S°W°: To the West, W°M°.

W°M°: Why are you placed like this?

S°W°: As the sun sets in the West to close the quarry for the day,...

W°M°: F° S°W°, where is the W°M° held?

S°W°: In the East, W°M°. (Belgian modern rite, RGLB).

Junior warden (J°W°) is « second surveillant » and Senior warden (S°W°) is « premier surveillant) in French.

This extract shows that the three brothers have the mission of leading the Lodge towards the Light.

The ritual of the following rites: modern Belgian, French rite, ancient and accepted Scottish rite, especially, speak of the numbers 3, 5 and 7. Here is an extract from the ritual concerning the numbers 3,5 and 7:

“W°M°: Where were you received as a Freemason?

Answer: In a just and perfect lodge.

W°M°: What does it take for a dressing room to be fair and perfect?

Answer: Three direct it, five enlighten it and seven make it just and perfect. »

The three “lights” leading the lodge are the Worshipful Master, and the Junior and Senior warden. We can also speak of “light” because these three Brothers must lead the Brothers towards the light. The five “lights” that illuminate the lodge are the three lights, plus the Brother Secretary and the Brother Speaker (Orator)

The Brother Speaker sits exactly under the Sun and the Brother Secretary, exactly under the Moon. It is therefore symbolically and because of the spatial arrangement, tools and cosmic elements that these two Brothers also illuminate the Lodge.

Junior and Senior warden are seated in their stalls, each near their Column to direct the Brothers of their Column. The North Column “J” (Jakin) for the Junior warden and the South Column “B” (Boaz) for the Senior warden (Columns reversed to the ancient and accepted Scottish rite).

The other three, the Worshipful Master, Secretary and Orator, have their stall in the East. The Worshipful Master is seated on the Throne of Solomon, to his right, the Brother Secretary, to his left the Brother Orator.

Finally, to be able to open a lodge (put it to work) you need at least seven Brother masters or members of the lodge. Visiting Brothers can replace absent Brothers who are members of the lodge. At the level of Master, in fact, it takes seven Masters to open the lodge.

But these numbers have multiple meanings: in masonry, in numerology, in Kabbalah, in the Holy Scriptures, in tarology, in divination, etc.

This work does not claim to be exhaustive, since it focuses on the symbols of Freemasonry. However it seemed important to me to also have an approach to the Sephirot since it appears on the triptych.

The Quest, 20X15, Ink on cardboard, 2017

Spiritual elevation of which knowledge is the nourishment is the quest of the mason.

Sources :

<https://scribe.fr>

Bruno Tosi, Les Trois grandes lumières, la règle, l'équerre et le compas, Cosmogonie, Juin 2016.

Rituel de la RL° Les Vrais Amis, 51, GLRB (Rite écossais ancien et accepté)

Rituel de la RL° Les Sept Piliers, 38, GLRB (Rite moderne belge)

De la RL° François-Charles de Velbrück, 16, GLRB

De la RL° Saint Charles de la Parfaite Harmonie

De la RL° La Lumière des Ardennes, 24, GLRB

De la RL° Le Carré Long, 10, GLRB

Archives de Loge.

3.Thoughts regarding Kabbalah and Freemasonry and concerning numbers.

The tree of life is made up of ten Sephiroth which is the « *stages of emanation* ». Each Sephira is associated with a number from 1 to 10.

« *The Sephiroth break down the stages of the descending divine flow which flows over the man who seeks to understand.* »

Source: ©<https://www.jepense.org/arbre-de-vie-kabbalistique-signification/>

There are four worlds regarding the Kabbalistic tree of life.

The first world is called “Atzilut”, or “emanation”, and is represented by two Sephirat: the Keter, that is, the crown and Chochmah (wisdom). This first world is close to infinity and cannot be known directly, because it is the Spirit of God.

The second world is called “Beriah”, or “creation”, corresponds to Binah which is the third Sephira. This world can only be penetrated and understood through a deep meditative experience: this concerns the whole of creation.

The Third World is called “Yetzirah” or “formation”. It is the formation of reality in the mystical and psychic domains. This Third World encompasses the following six Sephirat.

The fourth world is called “Assiyah” or “action” and corresponds to the last Sephira, that is to say “Malchut” or the “kingdom”. This is the physical universe, space and time and energy in matter: this is manifested reality.

Each world is a reflection of the previous one, but on a different level.

Kabbalah is considered the soul of the Torah; as man has a body and a spirit, likewise in the Jewish tradition, Kabbalah is the soul of the body which is the Torah. “The initiation of Kabbalah is therefore summed up in what we call Pschatt, Remez, Drouch, Sod”. Its acronym is “PARDES”.

The Torah is made up of five books called the Pentateuch: Genesis - Leviticus - Numbers - Deuteronomy. The study of the Torah is therefore the gateway to being able to approach the soul of the Torah which is Kabbalah.

There are four progressive levels of discovery and understanding of the Torah, here they are:

Pschatt is the first level. It is the capacity for concrete and historical interpretation of the Torah, on a literary level.

The Remez is the stage where the reader's mind begins to understand that there are codes in the Torah and that these must be able to be decoded. But at this level, the disciple is not yet able to decode them.

Drouch is a higher level of knowledge; it is when the disciple is able to detect the codes and crypts in the Torah, as well as the deciphering keys.

Sod is the highest level: possessing the keys, the disciple knows how to decode the codes and interpret them in a subtle way.

Here are the explanation of the numbers.

1: This is the Sefhira Kether (crown).

It is the divine Unity, the oneness of the divinity, infinite and unique of creation. It is the primordial source, with absence of duality, of division. It is the starting point of existence. On the Apprentice's Tracing Board Alpha & Omega Triptych, Sephirot is present and Kether is represented on the Tracing Board by the first point towards the East. In Freemasonry, the Divinity is represented in various ways: the eye in the Luminous Delta in the Scottish rite, ancient and accepted for example, the letter "G" present in the degree (or grade) of Fellow craft and by the Yod that can be seen on the Apprentice painting of the Alpha & Omega triptych.

2 : The Sefhira Hokhmah (divine Wisdom, divine reception and transmission).

It is also associated with relationship and union, the connection between beings. The 2 is also the symbolism of inner dialogue, the 2 symbolizes duality, opposition, otherness, but also complementarity. This recalls the fact that God created woman with a rib of man to complete his work. Male/female duality, spirit/matter, Light/darkness, but also a source of evolution with 3 becoming possible. In Freemasonry, the 2 brings to mind opposites, yet complementary, for example, Moon/Sun, Female/Male, Earth/Air, Water/Fire, the two Columns Jakin and Boaz which frame the door of the Temple, where the Brothers "receive their salaries" (ritual).

3 : The Sefhira Binah (understanding, intelligence and intuition) symbolizing the ghost of the world, multiplication through creation.

It is therefore Unity manifested by dynamic forms. Thus the Kabbalah Tree of Life presents 3 Triads, the first of which is formed by Kether, Hokhmah, Binah. Each Triad is the manifestation of aspects of Divinity. 3 is associated with creativity, multiplicity, but also artistic expression. 3 also symbolizes balance and the interactions of forces. In Freemasonry, can we not associate this first Triad with the WISDOM - STRENGTH - BEAUTY Columns? Or even to the three lights which should direct the lodge towards the light? We can also see the Luminous Delta in the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, referring to the Divine.

The number 3 is the age of the Apprentice and he moves 3 steps towards the East, putting himself in order when he enters and greets the Worshipful Master, then the Senior warden and then the Junior warden before he is not led by the Master of Ceremonies to take his place at the North Column. Note that when the apprentice salutes the 2 Supervisors successively, he must not turn his back on the Worshipful Master.

4 : Hesed (love), symbolizing the cosmological representation of the dimensions of reality.

In Kabbalah, we learn that there are 4 worlds: Atziluth (emanation), Briah (creation), Yetzirah (formation), Assiah (action). The 4 worlds each represent a level of consciousness and manifestation of existence. The 4 also symbolizes the 4 elements. In Freemasonry, we find the 4 elements: the Earth (Vitriol Reflection Cabinet), as well as the three elements that the layman will have to discover during his initiation (the 3 journeys WATER-AIR-FIRE) before receiving the Light. In Freemasonry, the ritual also speaks of the four directions: West/East and North/South.

Initiation into Freemasonry is a “rebirth”, like the stabilization of the existence of the being, like a solid foundation thanks to a spiritual quest, far from the material. It is therefore the search for harmony (some masons speak of the sought-after "egregore"). Isn't this the quest of a traditional mason respecting the "Landmarks"? This search for harmony must go through introspection and the search for light, in order to be able to progress. Excerpt from the ritual:

*“Worshipful Master: What are you doing in Freemasonry?
Answer: Conquer my passions and make progress in Freemasonry. »*

5: Gevurah (power), symbolizing the fifth world.

That is to say primordial Humanity. The fifth element completing the first 4 (Earth-water-air-fire) is the SPIRIT. The 5 therefore symbolizes the dynamic of change, the progression allowing transformation, the capacity to evolve towards a new level of consciousness. It is an invitation to spiritual exploration through an even more expanded consciousness.

In Freemasonry, the Follow craft is five years old. Shouldn't he learn to progress, broaden his field of vision by travelling, by improving his skills? The entire Follow craft degree ritual is fundamentally built on the five journeys. It is up to him to explore perception, to evolve in order to transform himself. This transformation can be called spiritual alchemy.

6: The Sephira Tipheret (beauty) symbolizes the 6.

Tipheret is the central point of harmony and spiritual perfection and has a central position between Hesed (love, forces of mercy) and Gevurah (strength of rigour, power). Spiritual perfection is Divine. We can think of the perfection of creation in 6 days. The 6 is drawn in a hexagram like the Star of David (but also the Seal of Solomon). In this hexagram we can perceive two equilateral triangles. Each triangle represents contrary, yet complementary, forces: Male/Female - Fire/Water - Sky/Earth (the sky also symbolizes air).

The 6 in Kabbalah is used to seek unity with the Divine. It is surprising to see that in astrology, the number 6 represents the meaning of sacrifice, love and self-giving. This

symbolism is strangely close to Christianity (gift of self, love of Brethren, etc.), but also to the harmony of creation: God who created the world in 6 days.

Could the number 6 represent the ideal being, like the Divine? By extension, would the 6 also imply the great responsibility of any organization, like that of the Universe and its creation? In Freemasonry, don't we talk about the four elements Fire/Water/Air/Earth? Can we not also see the oppositions and complementarities there?

Can't the mosaic pavement symbolize the collision of material interests with the spiritual? Between Light and Darkness, between Death and Life? Secular birth and Masonic rebirth through initiation passing from Earth to Light, thanks to a new breath of life (Air). To the four directions (North/South/East/West) called East/West/North/South in masonry, are added the vertical directions up/down called Zenith/Nadir in masonry.

7. Netzah (Victory) is another Sephira also representing a specific principle in creation.

In Freemasonry, the 7 is often present and intrigues Apprentices and Follow crafts. Creation reminds us of $6+1=7$, a reference to divine creation, the seventh day being the divine day of rest. Each day of creation is the manifestation of reality; thus, according to Kabbalah, there are 7 celestial spheres (heavens) representing 7 levels of consciousness (spiritual progression).

In Freemasonry, the 7 is often present and intrigues Apprentices and Follow crafts. So I decided to widen the field of vision a little further regarding the 7. The divine attributes are seven in number and are of the Divine essence, the seven Middot : mercy, rigour, beauty, victory, foundation, kingdom and knowledge. The 7 symbolizes fullness, completion, perfection.

In tarology, the 7 is the "*Triumph Chariot, the Chariot or the Triumph*". Arcana 7 is linked to the flaming sword. The 7 acts in the name of truth and Justice. The 7 is linked to the Divine, which is perfection. It is the FIRE that opens the 7 churches of the Apocalypse. At our human level, in alchemy, we encounter the acrostic VITRIOL, allowing us to find the Philosopher's Stone within us.

Vitriol is an acrostic word meaning "*Visita interiora Terrae Rectificando Invenies Occulum Lapidem*", which means that we must visit the interior of the EARTH (ourselves) and by rectifying (ourselves) you will find the hidden Stone.

There are two dimensions that interact at the level of the generation of the philosopher's stone: the masculine character and the feminine character. These characters are represented by the Moon (water, woman) and the Sun (Fire, man). The acrostic Vitriol is made up of 7 letters and 7 words are used for teaching. These 7 words symbolize, in alchemy, the Great Work.

The 7 points of the great star of Alchemy are of a sacred nature in reference to the 7 planets. The 7 is of the divine essence and the Great Star with 7 points surrounded by the double circle (male and female forces) shines like the Sun in the Temple of Knowledge.

Freemasonry is not only Judeo-Christian, but also alchemical and esoteric, in this we find sephirotic elements in Freemasonry.

The acrostic Vitriol takes on its full meaning when the layman is brought into the cavern (Earth) called the "*Chamber of Reflexion*" (only for master masons). He will have to meditate there and prepare for his initiation, which involves his symbolic death to return to life. The 7 corresponds to the degree (or grade) of Master.

Extracts from the ritual:

« *W^oM^o: How old are you?*
Answer: 7 years and over. »

On the Table of the Companion degree of the triptych, we can see 7 stars symbolizing the stars, the celestial vault, the Zenith, the immensity, the immeasurable and the inexpressible, the cosmic mystery and creation. We can also think of the 7 steps of the Master Mason, the 7 liberal arts. There are other connections to be made with the number seven : the 7 days of the week, the 7 musical notes, etc.

The Sephirot presents other numbers which are less mentioned in the Blue Lodge (that is to say the three degrees of the symbolic Lodge). So I will briefly address them.

In Freemasonry, we cannot help but think of a possible relationship between the symbolism of 7 (Netzah) and the Steps of the Master. In fact, the three steps of the Apprentice are taken in the same direction. The Apprentice, who is three years old, does not have the perception of all of what is happening around him and must remain silent precisely to listen and see in order to better understand his restricted environment at the level of knowledge. The visual sense and the auditory sense are therefore the main senses at this level.

We could say that he discovers and experiments in silence. He was profane and passed through the court inside the Temple to be initiated and receive the light. He discovered the first sacred space of the Temple called "Olam".

The Follow craft is five years old. He discovered the blazing star and the letter "G". Through his five trips, he broadened his knowledge. As a Follow craft he is encouraged to make journeys no longer in silence; he can speak with the permission given to him. He listens, he sees what is happening around him, but the "logos" appears and he speaks.

A third sense appears: the tactile sense, thanks to its organs of phonation (its tongue, its palate, its cheeks, its breath) which allows it to speak. The last two senses begin to develop, but this happens in a more internal way: feeling things rather than smelling (olfaction is internal and linked to touch). The last sense, taste, also begins to develop in an interior and more spiritual way. Indeed, the Follow craft will "taste" the pleasures of travelling, taste the sharing of ideas, the taste of learning, of serving, of helping, of loving his Brothers.

On the triptych concerning the Fellow crafts, we can see 7 stars symbolizing the stars, the celestial vault, the Zenith, the immensity, the immeasurable and the indescribable, the cosmic mystery and creation.

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He discovered the blazing star and the letter “G”. Through his five trips, he broadened his knowledge. As a Follow craft, he is encouraged to make journeys no longer in silence; he can speak with the permission given to him. He listens, he sees what is happening around him, but the “logos” appears and he speaks. A third sense appears: the tactile sense, thanks to its organs of phonation (its tongue, its palate, its cheeks, its breath) which allows it to speak.

The last two senses begin to develop, but this happens in a more internal way: feeling things rather than smelling (olfaction is internal and linked to touch). The last sense, taste, also begins to develop in an interior and more spiritual way. Indeed, the Follow craft will “taste” the pleasures of travelling, taste the sharing of ideas, the taste of learning, of serving, of helping, of loving his Brothers. Olfaction and taste are no longer just physical, but these two senses are activated to promote the elevation of the spirit.

The Follow craft steps bear witness to his evolution: to the Apprentice's three steps are added two other steps; the third which he will do obliquely towards the South and the fourth which he will do obliquely towards the North (note that in the modern Belgian rite, we start with the right foot and in the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, we start with the foot LEFT).

Symbolically, thanks to his steps (3+2), he discovers two other directions. He enters another dimension of knowledge. We can think that he discovered the second sacred space called « Hekal ». Finally when the Follow craft becomes a Master Mason, after having experienced Hiram's tragedy and he knows why speech is lost. Its rebirth is symbolic and conventional: the Brothers agree on the word « Macbenak » (the flesh leaves the bones), which allows continuity.

The assassination of the Master by the three fellow criminals involves the 5 senses: the remains found. Indeed, the Masonic search for the body involves the auditory, the discovery of the body, the visual; the fact of touching the corpse, the tactile. The olfactory is present symbolically by imagining putrefaction during the scene. The taste is even more symbolic, because spiritual: it is the bitter taste of knowing that it is the corpse of Master Hiram.

The Follow craft who has become Master will take two more steps to straddle Hiram's body then another step to regain stability, balance, good support and find himself right in front of the Altar. The Master's steps are therefore: the apprentice's steps (3 steps) + the Follow crafts' 2 steps, then the master's two steps to straddle the body and one step to regain balance and be in the exact extension of the 3 steps from the Apprentice, therefore 2+1 steps. If the 2 steps of the Follow craft mean the discovery of two additional directions allowing the expansion of knowledge, the 2 additional steps of the Master can mean « Chao ». The third and final step

allows you to regain your balance. This last step allows you to find harmony (Ordo AB chao) and move towards the « Debir » which is the « Holy of Holies ». So there are seven steps, plus one additional step, to Mastery. This is why the Master Mason will say that he is “7 years and over” (7+).

It is interesting to note that the arcana « *The Chariot* » of the Marseille tarot, being the seventh blade, represents the man who leads pulled by two horses. On a symbolic level, this seventh blade represents man's capacity to lead his life in a committed, dynamic manner; thus, the Chariot is the image of the desire to move forward, to progress in a thoughtful and autonomous manner. According to Paul, Marteau (1969), the abstract meaning of blade 7, The Chariot, means « *The material currents which carry man and force him always to be in motion* ».

Blade 7 is followed by 8 which symbolizes Justice, with the abstract meaning of balance. The abstract meaning of card 9, The Hermit, concerns the Inner Life. The number 7 in the Tarot therefore symbolizes progression which is a phase of accomplishment of the Fool who has been able to overcome difficult times, but he still has trials to overcome. The number 7 is sacred, because it is linked to the laws of life and the cosmos (the 7 planets for example). The 7 is sacred, because it follows the divine paths (creation).

Furthermore, if the number 7 symbolizes accomplishment, following victory over difficulties, the fact remains that it also predicts other trials to come which will be even more difficult (8 and 9). Thus accomplishment becomes an ultimate stage beyond which, however, progress will still be made. The Tarot can ask us about the links with Freemasonry. Indeed, in Freemasonry, in the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, if we reflect on the progression of the Freemason from the degree of Apprentice to the degree of Knight Kadosh (1° to 30°, excluding the administrative degrees 31°, 32° and 33°), we see that the Freemason must constantly question himself in order to progress, fighting to overcome his passions, as well as the difficulties of life. This endless necessary progression is linked to the fact that we do not hold the truth, the light, and that we must constantly seek it.

8: It is the Sephira Hod, which means “splendour”.

This Sephirate is linked to transcendence and access to a higher reality, with the expansion of consciousness and the expression of divine wisdom. The 8 represents the eighth day in Kabbalah where the higher level of consciousness transcends the 7 (6+1): it is therefore a spiritual level beyond the "space-time" limits. Finally, it is the spiritual journey leading to a reconnection to the divine source. The seventh blade of the tarot is Justice (a woman carries a sword in front of the Scales of cosmic justice).

9: Yesod which means Foundation.

This Sephira represents accomplishment and fullness. It is the transition from one cycle to another cycle, in the sense of a transformation and a renewal. 9 represents creative force and spiritual ascension.

10 :Malchut, which means Kingdom, symbolizes totality and unity.

This Sephira is at the bottom opposite Kether (Crown). The 10 reminds us of the ten commandments given to Moses by God. These are the moral and spiritual principles

necessary among men and the relationship with the divine. It is a number that invites contemplation and plenitude, in phase with the Universe and the Divine.

If we try to make a superposition, in Freemasonry, Malchut makes us think of Brother Roofer who guards the door of the Temple and is opposite the Worshipful Master seated in the chair of King Solomon.

Finally, Hokhmah and Binah can remind us of the two overseers, Kether being the Worshipful Master.

Sources :

Robert, Ambelain, La Kabbale pratique, introduction à l'étude de la Kabbale mystique et pratique, et à la mise en action de ses traditions et de ses symboles, en vue de la Théurgie, éd. Nicole Buisnière, 1990.

Roger, Gascon, Comprendre les secrets de la Kabbale, ée ; De Vecchi poche, 1994.

Lenain, la science cabalistique, éd. Traditionnelles, 1978.

Pierre, Manoury, le livre des talismans, éd. E.P.R., 1980

De l'homme à Dieu, Séphiroth et hiérarchies angéliques, 2^e édition, collection Izvor, nr 236, éd. Prosveta, 1996,

ISBN 2-8556-594-9.

Samuel, Aun, Weor, Curso esoterico, Kabala, 2^e éd. Colombie, 1977, version française.

Le Talmud (Torah orale) : <https://www.torah-box.com/torah-pdf/>

La Torah écrite : <https://www.torah-box.com/torah-pdf/>

<https://www.furet.com/media/pdf/feuilleter/9/7/8/2/4/1/4/2/9782414250578.pdf>

La Bible de Jerusalem, 2016, éd. Cerf.

La Kabbale : <https://www.furet.com/media/pdf/feuilleter/9/7/8/2/4/1/8/0/9782418003521.pdf>

Paul, Vulliaud, La Kabbale Juive [https://archive.org/details/PV-KJ/Vulliaud_Paul_-
_La_Kabbale_juive_Tome_I/](https://archive.org/details/PV-KJ/Vulliaud_Paul_-_La_Kabbale_juive_Tome_I/)

Ad, Franck, LA KABBALÉ ou La philosophie religieuse des Hébreux, 1843 – éd. Arbre d'Or, Suisse, 2009 : <https://www.arbredor.com/ebooks/Kabbale.pdf>

Rav Berg, Le pouvoir de la Kabbale, éd. J'ai Lu :

<https://excerpts.numilog.com/books/9782290366592.pdf>

<https://excerpts.numilog.com/books/9782732841984.pdf>

[https://psychanalyse.com/pdf/L%20ARBRE%20DE%20VIE%20KABBALISTIQUE.%20\(8%20Pages%20-%20386%20Ko\).pdf](https://psychanalyse.com/pdf/L%20ARBRE%20DE%20VIE%20KABBALISTIQUE.%20(8%20Pages%20-%20386%20Ko).pdf)

<https://fr.scribd.com>

<https://www.jepense.org/arbre-de-vie-kabbalistique-signification/>

Archives de loges

B.P., Grimaud, Ancien Tarot de Marseille, Explication des Arcanes majeurs et mineurs, J.M. Simon, 1969, Paris.

Paul, Marteau, Le Tarot de Marseille, 1969, Paris VI.

Chœur des chauves, 27X36, gouache sur carton, 1999, Sebök Ferenc.

4.Symbolism of the elements and the tools which appear on the Alpha & Omega triptych: their meaning in the rituals, as well as the synthesis of the perceptions that the Freemasons have of them.

In this part of the work, in the frames, I took up the perceptions collected from the Brothers, noting the definitions and explanations that they gave of the elements and tools chosen and used in Freemasonry. Repetitions have been eliminated. I added personal comments outside the framework.

The sun :

« The Sun represents fire, the masculine, ardour, strength.

The sun is represented by Mercury.

The sun is also the divine reason illuminating and radiating knowledge.

It can be associated with the element "fire".

The sun transmits its heat (fire) and its light ».

The moon :

« The Moon symbolizes the feminine, the Womb, but also the imagination giving ideas a particular and appropriate form.

It can be associated with the element "water".

Does not the Venerable Master symbolize the conscious principle illuminating

thanks to the Sun?

It symbolizes divine reason and light and thanks to the Moon, that is to say, imagination. The Sun and the Moon representing duality and “Male/Female” complementarity ».

The stars :

« The Celestial Vault and the Universe in connection with the Divine. But also the immeasurable Chain of Union in the cosmic immensity, creation of the Great Architect of the Universe.

The stars remind man that he is part of the Universe and that he has his place in the Cosmos. The stars therefore remind us of two essential elements of the construction of the Universe by the Great Architect: the microcosm and the macrocosm ».

This encourages us to be more humble, because it reminds us that the more we progress in knowledge and the closer our mind gets to Debir, the more we discover that we know very little.

Tracing board:

« The tracing board symbolizes the work of the Freemasons, their tracings which they erased before leaving.

The tracing board represents the work of the Brothers from Noon to Midnight, as well as their presence marked with a cross.

The tracing board represents a personal work to be exhibited to the Brothers of the Lodge.

The tracing board indicates that mason's work in a sacred space.

The cross indicates the Brothers present.

The tracing board is the symbol of work accomplished, but also to be done ».

In certain Lodges, Brother listeners can ask questions or offer reflections; in other Lodges, silence must reign on the Columns after the work presented (there are no discussions on the theme). On the apprentice degree, the tracing board is represented by a rectangle divided in two, containing a cross as well as four bars crossing in pairs.

The square:

Symbolically, the square means straightness in action. The square is a stationary tool. It is the tool (Jewel) which represents the Worshipful Master. The square also gives the measure, the extent like arms; it allows us to receive, encompass and protect like two walls at right angles. The square also symbolizes incorruptibility, discernment and wisdom.

The compass :

« The compass is a mobile tool for seeking truth in measurement.

It is the complementary tool of the square allowing to open the works.

Two essential tools for opening and closing the work of the Lodge.

These are tools that we have available in the Bible open to the Prologue of John.

The compass symbolizes searching with precision.

The compass allows you to search for the scattered Brothers.

The compass also involves thinking before action.

The compass implies the notion of tolerance and openness ».

There are two tools symbolizing the Freemason's progress in the three degrees of a Blue Lodge: the compass and the square. It is also between square and compass that we will always find Freemasons scattered across the surface of the Earth. Freemasonry also aims to bring together what is scattered.

The arrangement of the square and compass varies according to the degrees in a Blue Lodge and it is on the Altar where the three lights of Freemasonry are found (Volume of the Sacred Law, square and compass) that the two tools will be available.

For the Apprentice degree, the square is on the compass, because matter dominates the mind. For the degree of Fellow craft, the compass crosses with the square, because there is a rebalancing between matter and spirit. For the degree of Master, the compass is on the square, because spirit triumphs over matter.

The flaming sword:

« The flaming sword is the tool of the Worshipful Master.

It is with this tool that he will do justice, as Solomon used his sword to do justice in the Old Testament.

The Worshipful Master will administer the Oaths with the flaming sword.

The flaming sword symbolizes authority and impartiality.

The flaming sword is the symbol of fire in action ».

The mallet:

« There are four mallets in Freemasonry including that of the Venerable.

The W^oMaster's mallets punctuate the phases of the ritual and symbolize order and precision.

The blows struck by the W^oM^o followed by the first Warden, then the second Warden are symbolically strong to the extent that the blows go from the East to the South then the North and that the space of the Lodge are covered.

The Worshipful Master has a gavel and marks his authority.

There is a mallet for the Apprentice placed with a chisel on the rough Stone.

The mallet of the Venerable Master represents the will in action.

It is a symbol of power, of impartiality which reminds us of Solomon.

It is a tool that serves to guarantee order and serenity.

The three mallets punctuate the ritual and the space (1-2-3 blows) and thus create the triangular space formed by the Worshipful Master, the First and the Second Supervisor ».

The authority of the Venerable Master is real, because he has a police right, which allows him to have the Temple covered by a Brother who disrupts the Outfit. The two Wardens have a mallet during the execution of the ritual, to mark the episodes of the ritual and respond to the Worshipful Master. It is also a symbol of rigour.

The mallet placed on the rough stone with the chisel is that of the newly initiated Apprentice who, during his initiation, must carry out his first symbolic work, by striking with the chisel, 3 blows on the rough Stone (Modern Rite for example or in ancient and accepted Scottish rite).

The chisel:

« The chisel symbolizes discernment in research.

It is with the chisel that we can seek efficiency in work.

The chisel is used to square the rough stone.

The Apprentice will have to cut his rough stone with his mallet and chisel.

Cutting your stone means working on yourself.

The chisel and the mallet allow us to cut the stone, but the stone is us, to improve ourselves.

The chisel gives precise cuts and symbolically allows you to make progress in your Masonic journey.

With each stroke of the chisel, we rough up the rough stone, but symbolically, this can be the act of overcoming one's passions.

It's trying to rectify our bad inclinations, with the chisel and the mallet.

This could be greed, power, intolerance, the search for honour, etc. ».

This improvement helps to reach perfection, which also implies the fact that the Brother must be able to overcome his passions, his addictions, his inclinations. This journey must tend towards spiritual perfection.

The spiritual dimension among the Freemasons is inseparable from fraternal love. It is in this understanding that the symbolism of the Chain of Fraternal Union is important.

In a Lodge, where the search for spirituality associated with fraternal love exists, it is a Lodge where Order, Peace and Harmony are the cornerstones.

Unfortunately, it often happens that the “metals” do not stay outside the Temple and disputes, dissensions, the search for power, rivalries, clannishness in the Lodge tarnish the Works.

Therefore, there is not what we call “ORDO AB CHAO”.

We are only men and the question is whether we are worthy of being Masons.

The Level :

« The level is also a standard insofar as it gives the right direction.

The level allows you to see if the construction is plumb; concerning man.

The level allows us to question ourselves and see if our action is good, necessary and useful.

Symbolically, the level allows the correct implementation of knowledge.

The directions are horizontal and vertical (plumb line attached to the triangle)

It is the search for the equality of the stones used to make the wall; symbolically, the level can concern the Brothers of a Lodge (the stones) or ourselves.

It is the tool that allows you to build with precision.

The level is a tool that makes possible the order of work like the ruler, compass and square.

It is the level and the perpendicular which will make it possible to distinguish the Brother from the Profane who knows neither the gesture nor its meaning.

The level is triangular and a plumb line is joined to it to measure horizontality and verticality: horizontal and vertical give the perpendicular, like the order sign in Lodge.

The plumb line encourages introspection, to “descend into oneself”.

The plumb line shows the direction and the precise space to be respected.

It is a call to get rid of our metals, our prejudices, our bad inclinations.

The plumb bob also gives an idea of the importance of rigour.

The square-shaped triangle checks stability and precision in actions ».

Symbolically, doesn't the level allow us to control our actions so that they are done to the "right extent"? The horizontality and the verticality give a double measure. In some Lodges, there is a single plumb bob that hangs above the Lodge board.

The Ruler :

*« The ruler symbolizes precision and foresight in execution.
Research in the work is rigour.
The ruler allows control in execution.
The ruler allows you to trace and control or compare.
The ruler allows you to check the straightness of the plan for drawing and building.
The ruler is the tool that requires the Brother to be rigorous in his ideas and his actions.
The ruler allows the measurement of things, actions, speech, evaluation and control.
The ruler also symbolizes respect for "Landmarks".
The ruler involves being faithful to one's oaths.
The ruler brings to mind rigour, limits and direction ».*

Can't the ruler check for deviations? Injustices and disparities versus constant gaps?
Isn't the ruler a measure and a direction concerning our progress?

The lever :

*« The lever represents power in action.
The lever allows you to mobilize the stone and adjust it in relation to the others.
Leverage is an essential tool to mobilize us to the right extent.
The lever allows adjustments to construct the building.
Concerning the mason, the lever allows you to be motivated in the action that seems insurmountable.
Lever makes possible what is normally impossible.
Therefore, the lever is an instrument that generates hope.
The approach is symbolic and concerns working on ourselves thanks to the lever: having the will and the power to improve ».*

As in the days of the cathedral builders, the workers at work had to work together to succeed in the construction project. Indeed, using a lever often involves the presence and help of others.

Thus the Brother is surrounded by his Brothers to build spirituality and fraternity.
As the ritual says:

"...together we can do anything".

The trowel :

*« The trowel is the tool used to make mortar, but also to put the binder between the cut stones or bricks to construct the building.
The Trowel represents the love of the Brothers and cohesion.
Symbolically, this recalls the importance of benevolence and brotherly love necessary in the Lodge.
The Trowel helps create harmony.*

Concretely, the trowel is the tool allowing us to work on ourselves first so that we can feel good about ourselves and then so that we can help our Brothers who are not feeling well. The Trowel involves working for a group, the Brothers of the Lodge to seek peace and mind Fraternal ».

Extract from the ritual, during an oath taken before the Altar:

« ...I promise and swear to love my brothers... »

Isn't the Trowel the tool par excellence that must be held in the hand by each Brother, in the Lodge and outside the Lodge. The Trowel gives us the opportunity to measure the quantity of mortar that must be put between the stones.

Symbolically, isn't this the amount of attention we should have towards a Brother?

The cubic stone (or pointed cubic stone) :

« The cubic stone is the symbol of full Masonic achievement.

The stone (ourselves) was well squared, cut with precision, able to fit among the stones of the building, for example the Lodge.

Concretely, a Lodge can only function if there is a centripetal force, with a common desire of the Brothers to build the fraternal spirit.

The cubic stone is a first achievement of the Fellow craft who must continue his efforts to progress in spirituality.

The pointed cubic stone involves comparing my stone to my Brother's stone to find out if the two stones can fit into the building; so this also involves working together ».

Cutting a rough stone into a pointed cubic stone requires personal work and work in consultation with the other Brothers in order to be able to place the stones precisely to each other. Symbolically, work in the lodge is individual work (individual preparation) and group work. This requires on the part of the Brothers, assiduity and a sought-after spiritual journey, common and shared goals.

If Freemasonry is not necessary for the « profane », because other paths exist for spiritual research, Freemasonry needs Brothers who aspire to more spirituality and who cultivate the fraternal spirit. Concerning the cubic stone, it is interesting to note that the “Saint” and the “Holy of Holies” were in the shape of a cube.

Knowledge of the ritual is the basic food of the spiritual plan, personal or group research allows a journey where ideally, the Brothers are concerned with helping their Brothers. The participation of Brothers in Lodge implies an open, rigorous and fraternal spirit.

The Luminous Delta appearing on the Apprentice table:

« Symbolically, the luminous Delta will transmit knowledge, with its radiation.

It is the triangle with the eye of the divine which sees all and this triangle transmits its radiance to the Lodge.

The radiation of the Delta, with the sun, will dazzle the entire East, which allows the W^oMaster to lead the Brothers towards more light.

The window located in the East represents the W^o Master and this window receives its radiation from the luminous Delta, but the sun also illuminates the East.

Thanks to the Luminous Delta, the W^o Master will be able to transmit light, as he does by transmitting fire to light the candles of the first and second supervisors. It is the luminous Delta which gives wisdom to the W^oMaster, his strength thanks to the sun. Symbolically, the Delta watches over the Works ».

The Delta, which is the fourth letter of the Greek alphabet, is a triangle which radiates its brilliance on the three Great Lights found on the Altar: the Volume of the sacred law, the square and the compass.

The W^o Master's task is to transmit light, it is also through his wisdom, his rigour and his incorruptibility that he can transmit knowledge; he is helped by his two Supervisors. In the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, in the East, between the Sun and the Moon, there is the luminous Delta with an eye or sometimes a Yod or a simple point. At the third degree of Master on the coffin, there is an acacia branch and a delta.

The Delta on the tomb of Hiram murdered by three treacherous Brothers represents the lost light, the lost word.

The Luminous Delta is therefore the very essence of light and is a source of balance and harmony.

The two Columns J and B:

« The two columns separate the Brothers seated in the North or the South. Column "J" accommodates Apprentices, while Column "B" accommodates Fellow crafts, but Master Masons sit wherever they wish. It is at the columns that the Brothers symbolically receive their salaries. "J" means "Jakin" and "B" means "Boaz". This is the name of the two brass pillars according to the Hebrew Bible, placed by Solomon. The two columns represent duality and complementarity. Boaz means "in strength or in him, strength. " Jakin" means "he will establish" or "he will found". Boaz shows the will and symbolically the intention of the spirit; Jakin is more into action and concreteness. Boaz and Jachin are two complementary columns, because Boaz is more in the spiritual dimension ».

King Solomon had two bronze pillars placed at the entrance to the Temple of Jerusalem (I King, 7, 13-21 and the book of chronicles 3,17). The two columns are complementary, but different. Column "J" strengthens, creates stability (matter) and column "B" creates power (spirit). Thus Boaz encourages introspection and is more spiritual (aerial), while Jachin is the one who shapes and creates with his hands, he is active (terrestrial).

In the modern Belgian rite and the French rite, Column "J" (Jakin) is located near the door of the Lodge, towards the North, where the stall of the second Warden is located; Column "B" (Boaz) is located near the door of the Lodge, towards the South, where the stall of the first Warden is located. In the ancient and accepted Scottish Rite, Columns "J" and "B" will be reversed.

The tree of life is made up of three pillars: the pillar of mercy associated with Boaz and Jachin is the pillar of rigor (shaper, builder, founder). Where then is the third pillar? In the centre of the Lodge equidistant from the two columns. This third pillar or column is ourselves! We are the awareness of the Lodge, because we have been initiated.

But the children of light also find themselves between square and compass. Finally, in Freemasonry, Boaz is associated with the Winter Solsticial Festival (Saint John the Evangelist) in the sense that in masonry, the Brothers work from NOON to MIDNIGHT, while Jakin is associated with the summer solstice (John the Baptist).

Boaz implies more interiority and work on oneself and the Winter Solstice, symbolically the culmination of purification through spiritual work. After the Winter Solstice, the Sun reappears, in force, and it is the moment of its ascension with its brilliance and warmth. This new stage is manifested by the earth which buds and takes possession of time and space. Jakin is here and it is the moment of renewal, emerging from the earth (matter), reintegrating the spirit for a new phase of fulfilment.

Grenades:

« The pomegranate is a symbol of fertility and pomegranates are found on both columns. However there are boxes where the earth and the moon are found there.

The pomegranate can symbolize a lodge with the grains inside, that is to say the Brothers. The pomegranate has a hard shell protecting the grains, just as the Lodge protects the Brothers from unwelcome people, thanks to the closure of the temple and the presence of the brother roofer, also called brother "tyler".

The pomegranate symbolizes the cohesion of the Brothers in a Lodge where harmony reigns. The pomegranate represents brotherly love.

The pomegranate symbolizes the unity of the multitude of grains in the fruit, that is to say the Brothers in the Lodge.

The pomegranate with its grains is like the Brothers who are between square and compass in a place known only to the widow's children.

The six red pomegranates placed on the columns bring to mind creation and the fire of life. The grains of the pomegranate can make us think of the masons scattered across the surface of the Earth and who are nevertheless between the square and the compass.

Is there no possible link between the seeds of the pomegranate symbolizing fertility and the ultimate goal of Freemasonry which is to initiate profane people? ».

In the lodge, the pomegranates (when there are any on the columns) are not very visible and few masons know that it is not a tool, but a decorative element of the lodge which is essential, because the pomegranates represent the Lodge: a discreet, closed place where only the initiated meet, like the grains of pomegranates well protected by a very solid skin.

On the Triptych we can see pomegranates on the columns, 6 in number for each column. As a reminder, 6 represents accomplishment (creation in 6 days) and harmony as well as spiritual perfection.

In China, even today, the custom is to offer pomegranates to newlyweds to wish them many children.

In the Zoroastrian religion, the pomegranate symbolized eternal life because of its evergreen foliage. It is a symbol of fertility, but also of resurrection and for Freemasons, rebirth. It is interesting to learn that for John of the Cross "the seeds of the pomegranate are the symbol of the innumerable effects of divine perfection" (Irène Mainguy).

Christian Freemasonry was undoubtedly inspired by biblical texts; in fact, in Jeremiah, King 1, we can read that on each column of Solomon's temple, there were pomegranates of brass.

The Lake of Love or Serrated Tussock:

« The tassel is a rope where there are "intertwinings" symbolizing the fraternal chain. The tuft is also called the lake of love which must be the cement connecting the Brothers. The tassel is a knotted or intertwined rope; there are some in my lodge and start from the East to encompass the South and the North to signify fraternity and cohesion. The Hoop demarcates the sacred space. The Hoop with intertwining can mean the Chain of Brothers. The Tuft can symbolize protection and the place known only to the children of light. The fact that the Hoop surrounds the Lodge is a delimitation of the sacred space. The tuft or lake of love materializes the fraternal spirit and the desire to love one's Brothers. The Lake of Love constantly reminds us that we must love our Brothers. When we do the Chain of Union, I think of the Serrated Tuft ».

A rope with three knots can be seen in the Apprentice painting. This rope represents the Chain of fraternal union, but also the fact that it is from Above that spirituality and Love can come. This element is also called "Lake of Love", because the flow of love spreads without limits. The three knots refer to the age of the Apprentice, but also to the responsibility of the "lights" who direct the Lodge (Worshipful Master and the two Wardens). By adding three knots to this rope, I wanted to see the theological virtues "Faith – Hope – Charity". On some lodge tables, there are 5 knots or seven knots, depending on the degree (Companion board or Master board).

The 3 windows:

« The windows symbolize the light received by the Brothers. There are 3 windows which are associated with apprentices having little light, with companions from the South, having a little more light and the W^oM^o, who symbolically holds the wisdom of Solomon and has a lot of light. The three windows remind us that we must make progress in Freemasonry. The three windows remind us that it is by searching diligently that we can aspire to more light. The windows have six panes on the Lodge painting, undoubtedly to recall creation, and therefore the divine. Windows are like mirrors reflecting light, that is, knowledge ».

The first window is near the East, therefore near the Sun. The light is strong, because there is the Chair of Solomon renowned for his wisdom; the first window is that of the Worshipful Master and his equals, the Masters of the Lodge.

The second window concerns Companions who have already acquired knowledge, know the meaning of the blazing star and are 5 years old. However, they still have to square their stone a lot, with strength and precision in order to deserve access to the Master's word. Their window has fewer light reflections.

The third window which reflects a very pale light is that of the Apprentices, because the ritual says: « ...they perceive only a faint light ».

Silence is golden for Apprentices. It should be noted that the Apprentices window is located above the Companions window which is further to the south and towards the East. Logically, the Apprentice's window should be in the North, but this is practically impossible, because in Jerusalem, the northern ramparts, located on the side of the Gehenna valley, there was no opening. Thus the Apprentice's window on the lodge table of the triptych is symbolically on the right below the Fellow craft's window and not on the left.

We can notice that the three windows are located at three levels which we can define as being in three different and progressive spaces or dimensions in knowledge: first window of the Apprentice where there is only a weak light, corresponding to "Ulam" – second window, of the Fellow craft, where there is more light, the "Hekal" – the third window of the Mastery corresponding to the "Debir". On the Triptych we can see the arrangement of the windows.

The Mosaic Pavement:

« The mosaic pavement symbolizes duality and the clash of interests.

The mosaic paving stone represents, symbolically, the opposite and the complementary which must tend towards balance.

The cobblestones are black and white, like darkness and light.

The mosaic tile makes me think of life and death, a path, or a rebirth.

The mosaic paving translates coherence and balance.

The Mosaic Pavement is the representation of cut stones that fit perfectly, and the stones are men with their good sides and their bad sides.

The mosaic tile makes me think of truth and its opposite: what is true today may no longer be true tomorrow, so the mosaic tile encourages us to deviate from our certainties.

The mosaic paving brings out balance and harmony.

The mosaic tile makes me think of the complementarity of a man/woman, yin and yang, but also of duality.

There is a connection to be made between the Mosaic Pavement and Divinity, as the Mosaic Pavement can represent light and darkness, as opposing pairs.

The Mosaic Pavement can represent revenge (black) and love (white).

The Mosaic Pavement presents two possible poles: good and evil.

The squares of the Mosaic Pavement make me think of order and complementarity.

The Mosaic Pavement can be interpreted as a balance (white and black) resulting in unity ».

The mosaic pavement presents a great wealth of interpretation.

The Gothic Vault:

« For this element of the Lodge Table, I did not question the Brothers since it is a personal element added to the triptych.

The triptych contains an arched Gothic construction alluding to the equally Christian origins of Freemasonry.

But if cathedral builders built Temples to the Glory of God, churches pointing towards the sky meant "being in relationship with the divine", and receiving grace.

For the traditional Freemason, it is receiving the Light that is within us, but we will have to work on ourselves to discover it ».

The pyramid with the symbolism of time:

For this element of the Lodge Table, I did not question the Brothers since it is a personal element added to the triptych.

The triptych contains a pyramid. This pyramid is built from Earth to Heaven. The pyramid has a top pointing towards the sky. Everything is a symbol in Freemasonry. With the pyramid, I wanted to symbolize the construction of the builders who also aspired to light.

The tip of the pyramid indicates that light comes from above and that this unique light radiates downwards everywhere. It is also a translation of the ritual which says this:

“What is Above is Below...”

The Yod appearing in the centre of the concentric circles:

« The Yod represents the divine. It is a letter of the Hebrew alphabet which is associated with the number one, i.e. Unity or uniqueness. The Yod sometimes replaces the eye in the sacred triangle among the Scots. I have already seen a Yod or even a dot; it symbolizes Yahweh. The Yod represents the omnipresence of the divine ».

Yod is the tenth letter of the Hebrew alphabet, its numerical value being 10, which, as we saw previously, invites contemplation and plenitude.

The Yod is the culmination and represents the Divine.

In Freemasonry, the Yod is present in certain Lodge Tables. Therefore, the Yod represents the Grand Architect of the Universe in Freemasonry. The Yod or point can replace the eye in the Luminous Delta. The Yod synthesizes the tetragram Yod-Hé-Vav-Hé (Yavé).

Concentric circles:

In the triptych we can see concentric circles. It is an allusion to the 7 divine heavens of Kabbalah. Concentric circles also signify perfection through the absence of the angle and the perpetual and infinite movement of the Universe. The concentric circles also allude to the levels of knowledge and the spiritual journey of the Brothers who wish to journey towards the Debir, in order to get closer to the Great Architect of the Universe.

The seven drops of blood:

« The blood represents the blood of Master Hiram the architect. The 3 Fellow crafts requested the word from the Master who refused to give them and the master received three blows in turn. Drops are often used to symbolize Hiram's shed blood. There are seven drops of blood to symbolize Hiram who was Master.

Seven drops of blood, because three evil Fellow crafts have killed the sacred (Lost Word). "Seven" refers to perfection and accomplishment; the seven drops of blood symbolize the fact that Hiram's murderers wanted to appropriate this perfection by force. The seven drops symbolize the speech that is lost by the death of Hiram.

The blood refers to the apron that the Worshipful Master must check: “if the apron is pure and without stain”. On the triptych, at the Master's level, we see seven drops of blood surrounding the coffin ».

The seven drops refer to the symbolism of 7 in Kabbalah. By killing the Master architect Hiram, the three treacherous Fellow craft killed the word (the Master's word), but also the Light, knowledge, perfection. They also killed the one who was “seven years and over” according to the Masonic ritual.

Alpha & Omega, 20x15, inks on cardboard, 2020, Sebök Ferenc.

Hiram's Tomb:

*« The coffin symbolizes Hiram's murder.
The Tomb is part of the legend of Hiram.*

Hiram represents every Master Mason on the face of the Earth.

Hiram is the Master architect of Solomon who was killed by three companions and the Tomb or catafalque is testimony to this.

The tomb of Hiram signifies the murder of Hiram, but also the death which is followed by the resurrection ».

By analysing the triptych, we see that Hiram's coffin is oriented upside down, with his head towards the West. I see it as a symbol of disorder in the sense that the Master no longer has his head in the East, turned towards the West. "Ordo AB chaos" no longer exists, knowledge in the East lost... "the word is lost".

The Blue Lodge being a so-called lodge of Saint John, I cannot help but make the link between the Prologue of John and the "lost word" during the assassination of Hiram (the Darkness seems to have won).

The ritual takes up elements of the Prologue when the Worshipful Master says at the closing of the Lodge in the ancient and accepted Scottish rite: "...The light shines in the Darkness, but the Darkness has not received it".

The Acacia Branch:

« Acacia is associated with Master Hiram and by extension with Master Masons who lived the legend of Hiram murdered by three evil companions.

Acacia symbolizes incorruptibility.

Acacia symbolizes rot-proof.

The acacia is associated with the body of Hiram found ».

In the legend of Hiram, the acacia is a landmark to find Hiram.

Indeed, in ancient and accepted Scottish ritual, the ritual says this:

Right W^oMaster, we found a newly dug tomb, which we presume to be that of our Master Hiram. I planted an acacia branch there.

If this is so, my WW^o Brethren, we must unite our efforts. With two other Master Masons, I will join you.

Here is the tomb where the acacia branch is planted.

Ah, Lord, it is the Architect!...

In Freemasonry, the acacia therefore represents the body of Hiram found and it is linked to the Master. This is the reason why the acacia branch is a sign worn by many Brother Masters, who, if asked about their grade and quality, will answer:

"The acacia is known to me."

That is to say that they experienced the legend of Hiram and that they acquired the degree of Master.

Sources:

Henri, Blandin, The Indispensable Luminous Delta, Chaîne d'Union 2010/3 (No. 53), pp; 72 to 75.
Irène, Mainguy, Symbolic of the grades of perfection and the orders of wisdom or Thorough mastery: in the ancient and accepted Scottish and French rites, EAN:9782844542243, Dervy.
Irène, Mainguy, Initiations and Masonic initiation, ISBN: 979-1-02-420567-0, Dervy.
René, Guenon, Symbol of sacred science, ISBN: 979-1-02-420649-3, Dervy.
René, Guenon, Traditional forms and cosmic cycles, ISBN: 979-1-02-420650-9, Dervy.
René, Guenon, The symbolism of the cross, ISBN: 979-1-02-420573-1, Dervy.
Henri Pornon, What is the role of sacred geography in symbolic lodge, ISBN: 979-1-02-421789-5, Dervy.
Papus, Methodical treatise on occult science, ed. Georges Carré, 1891.
Ritual of the RL° True Friends, 51, GLRB
Ritual of the RL° François-Charles de Velbrück, 16, GLRB
Ritual of the RL° Le Carré Long, 10, Orient de Charleroi, GLRB
Ritual of the RL° France, 9, Orient of Budapest, GLSH
Ritual of the RL° La Lumière des Ardennes, 24, Orient de Forrières, GLRB
Ritual of the RL° The seven pillars, 38, Orient de Liège, GLRB
Ritual of the RL° Saint-Charles of Perfect Harmony, 43, Orient de Bouillon, GLRB
Ritual of the RL° Egyenlőség, Orient of Budapest, GLSH
Planches des Loges Archives
Collection of statements and perceptions of Freemasons.
<https://rufso.ac.cd/journal/rjsse/tag/ferenc-sebok/>

5.Hiram and his symbolism

In the ritual of the ancient and accepted Scottish Rite, the Companion who requested a salary increase is a Master in the making. During the ritual, he replaces Hiram's body and symbolizes a rebirth.

Indeed, the companion symbolically dies to be born again, discovering new horizons full of pitfalls. At the level of Master, he discovers a new dimension concerning his Brothers; indeed, the prudence which is revealed by these words in the ritual:

« *I would like to trust my Brothers* ».

This prudence is discovered by the legend lived by the Fellow craft who will be reborn to become Master. Indeed, the legend highlights the fact that among the Brothers there can be bad Fellow craft, traitors, because man is not perfect and must constantly make progress on himself to improve. Man is therefore perfectible, provided that he evolves by seeking Light.

Hiram dies as the profane dies during his initiation and then is reborn by receiving the Light after his travels evoking the Elements. This rebirth offers the possibility of progressing towards the Light.

During the ceremony, the three fellow felons represent the three principal officers of the Lodge, that is to say the Worshipful Master, the first Warden and the second Warden. This legend also teaches us that our actions must be done in moderation, being careful that our passions do not take over. No mason is therefore safe from himself! This is why he must constantly cut his stone as soon as he has received the Light thanks to his initiation to the Apprentice degree.

He will have to look at himself in the Mirror second-hand to discover his own judge. The ritual will take him five journeys, he will discover the existence of the blazing star, with the letter "G" which he will have to try to understand as he continues his initiatory journey.

To be received at the rank of Master, he will discover Hiram dead and will symbolically take his place and then be reborn like the Phoenix is reborn from its ashes, through the five Points of Perfection of Mastery. According to the rite, lying down and covered with a black shroud, he will hear say: "*MacBenac*" or "*Moabon*", according to the rite, and will feel a hand taking his and will hear the exclamation of horror :

« The flesh leaves the bones !... ».

The ritual mainly uses two senses: hearing and touch, without vision in this stage of the ritual. When raised (reborn) by the five Points of Perfection, the visual sense will reappear, associating with the auditory and tactile senses.

The instruction of the third degree of Master is symbolically strong. This instruction teaches that the J° Warden, bearer of the Plumb Bob, should possess sufficient knowledge to overcome his passions, otherwise it is ignorance that would precipitate him into the abysses of felony.

The S° Warden, for his part, who is the bearer of the Level, should be able to shed light on the Works of his Brothers, unless his passions, his felony and his fanaticism drive him into blindness.

The third main actor, who is the Worshipful Master in the murder of Hiram, is the third evil Fellow craft. This last actor should lead the Works with wisdom, tolerance, great availability, far from personal concerns and intrigues, showing brotherly love.

He will have to ensure the harmony of the lodge and above all rule out the desire to retain power after his mandate has come to an end. In certain rites, the Venerable Master having left the Chair of Solomon will become the Brother Roofer or Outer Roofer.

The legend of Hiram invites us to reflect on our hidden, excessive ambitions which tarnish our quality as masons and precipitate us towards the abyss of madness of grandeur.

The Mallet is the symbol of the Master's authority, certainly, but it must be fraternal and incorruptible, rigorous, otherwise the mallet becomes a murderous instrument as the legend of Hiram shows, since it is ultimately a blow of the mallet which killed Hiram!

The Gavel represents not only authority, but the desire to establish order (Ordo AB chao). Order is the "sine qua non" condition for respect and the possibility of fraternity in the Lodge. Not knowing how to tame one's passions and limiting oneself to subjective perceptions risks making men sink into madness.

Indeed, hasty actions can be regrettable and destructive. Unfortunately, all this can also happen in a Lodge where the "Sacred" space is replaced by conflicts, profane concerns: often, the merchants of the Temple are not far away.

The mason must work on himself and make room for the seven liberal arts and be in search of spirituality in love of Brothers

With the staging of Hiram's murder and resurrection, the rite becomes the essence of speculative Freemasonry. This legend allows us to experience the last phase of the mason's initiation into the so-called "Blue" Lodge. This legend makes us discover the immanence described in the ritual: "what is Above is Below and what is Below is Above".

The raising of the body by the five points of Perfection allows a symbolic substitution with Hiram, to be reborn. The new Master thus passes from the horizontal terrestrial plane to the sky, via the vertical plane serving as a link. The death of Hiram ultimately makes us discover four essential dimensions in our life as a mason.

A moral dimension first, which is close to probity and the questioning of our actions: it teaches us what is just and rational. This dimension reminds us to keep the secret of the Master newly agreed between Brother Masters. This secret to keep, also implies being faithful to one's Oaths.

The second dimension is ethical. It is a dimension which implies reflection concerning our actions, not having bad intentions towards our Brothers. Harmony is therefore constantly sought to avoid Chaos. This dimension involves congruity, empathy and charitable spirit. The third is the symbolic dimension, that is to say the spiritual dimension and therefore the search for understanding of the Sacred. Without this dimension, no progression towards knowledge, no accomplishment is possible; in this, this third dimension refers to the divine.

The legend of Hiram makes us discover man and his universe in relation to death and the breath of life (Ruah or Pneuma) which is of the Divine essence. In the macrocosm, this makes us reflect on the meaning of the appearance and disappearance of the stars, but also concerning the meaning of the Winter Solstice followed by the Summer Solstice, where we see the Sun reborn.

In Freemasonry, the ritual says this: "Alone we can do nothing, together we can do everything". In the Holy Scriptures we find an analogy to this. Here are the words of Jesus:

« Truly, truly, I say to you, unless the grain of wheat that falls into the ground dies, it remains alone; if, on the contrary, it dies, it bears fruit in abundance ».

Finally, there is an initiatory dimension in the legend of Hiram: the Fellow craft who is a Master in the making is suspected of murder, which is the reason why the W^o Master asks to see his Companion apron which has the lowered bib. The Fellow craft therefore passes a test of honourability (he has an apron without blood stains or not). Then he is killed, because he takes Hiram's place.

Finally, it is raised by the five Points of Perfection (death and resurrection). The new Master learns that he is becoming a new being who must embark on the path of spiritual research. His quest must not find rest, since he must overcome his passions and constantly make progress in Freemasonry (progress on himself). His struggle is therefore threefold: to overcome his passions - to make progress in Freemasonry - to cultivate fraternal love.

I will end my reflection by recalling our duty to build the Universal Chain.

Through this duty, the legend of Hiram refers us to Life (creation) rather than Death which is only a path. The Volume of the Sacred Law open to the Prologue of John, on which the Compass is placed on the Square, we can read this:

“The light shines in the Darkness, but the Darkness has not received it.”

If we are not perfect, we can be improved if we choose the path towards Light rather than sinking into futility and Darkness.

La lumière luit dans les ténèbres II, 50x40 acrylique sur panneau de bois, 2016, Ferenc Sebök.

6. In the legend of Hiram, what does the "Three evil Fellow craft" represent?

Mircea Eliade demonstrated that every human community and association needs a founding myth. This myth is based on the assassination of the Architect Hiram of King Solomon by three Felon Companions.

The Old Testament helps fuel this myth in 1 King, 7, verses 13-14, even if the biblical basis is very weak.

In the legend, Hiram receives three Companions who want to obtain the word of the Master. To do this, they successively use three tools to make him confess, which Master Hiram refuses. On the third blow from a mallet, Hiram dies.

Extracts from the ritual of the RL° Les Vrais Amis, 51, GLRB, with the steps of the Master:

« ... We had a Master who united all the perfections. His name was Hiram and he was the son of a widow. He was a skilled architect. The King of Tiro had sent him to Solomon, who had entrusted him with the construction of the Temple in Jerusalem and the direction of the multitude of workers.

Hiram had distributed the workers into three classes: the Apprentices, the Fellow crafts and the Masters, who had signs, words and touches to be recognized and receive their wages, the Apprentices near column B..., the Fellow craft near column J... and the Masters in the "Middle Chamber" (only for masters).

The work was nearing its end when three Fellow crafts, ignorant, perverse and ambitious, seeing that they had not been able to obtain Mastery, plotted to snatch by violence the word which would make them like the Masters...

Hiram first went towards the West Gate where the first accomplice asked him for Master's word. Hiram replied that he could not receive him in this way, that he had to do his time and that he, Hiram, was not authorized to give him the Master's word alone. Not satisfied with this response, the evil Fellow craft dealt him a 24-inch ruler across the throat.

Hiram then fled to the South Gate.

At the South Gate, he found the second accomplice, who made the same request to him, and received the same response. Angered, the bad Fellow craft will give Hiram a violent blow with a Square on the breast. This time again, Hiram was able to escape staggeringly, managing to reach the Gate of the East. The third traitor made the same request and received the same refusal. He struck Hiram so violently on the forehead with a mallet that Master Hiram died...

... My WW° BB° ... Hiram has perished and the Word is lost...

... Since then, darkness has invaded the world, confusion has ensued in the work of the Temple. Ignorance, lies and ambition confuse materials, layouts and tools, and give rise to discord. Hiram alone possessed the secret of the work begun. We must find his body, and perhaps, some bits of his knowledge... » (ritual, AASR, « Les Vrais Amis, 51, RGLB).

The evil Fellow crafts therefore represent ambition, lies, ignorance.

These three characteristics linked to man prevent all humanity, all spiritual progression.

Sources :

Rituel de la RL° Les Vrais amis, 51, GLRB

Rituel de la RL° François-Charles de Velbrück, 16, GLRB

Rituel de la RL° Le CarréLong, 10, GLRB

Rituel de la RL° Iris, 42, GLRB

Rituel de la RL° Egyenlőség, Orient de Budapest, GLSH

Rituel de la RL° Sambre & Meuse, 25, Orient de Namur, GLRB

Archives de Planches de Loges

Les Secrets de la Loge, n° 20, Hiram, le Temple et Salomon, Magazine de la Franc-maçonnerie, avril 2017.

Recueil des perceptions des Francs-maçons interrogés.

Mircea, Eliade, The Sacred and The Profane: The Nature of Religion Paperback – October 23, 1987.

Mircea, Eliade, The Forge and the Crucible: The Origins and Structure of Alchemy Paperback – March 15, 1979.

Tracing board : « Ce qui fut, ce qui est, ce qui sera », 90X180, acrylic on wood, 2016, Ferenc Sebök. Collection de la RL° Sambre & Meuse, 25, Orient de Namur, Belgique.